

CINEMATIC NARRATIVES IN PROMOTING THE PUBLIC'S PERCEPTIONS OF AGRICULTURE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: Agricultural innovation is vital to addressing food security challenges in Nigeria, yet the public's perceptions often shape the acceptance and adoption of these innovations. The population of the study are media professionals from Ogun State Chapter of Nigerian Union of Journalists and farmers in Abeokuta South. The study made use of a purposive sampling technique and a sample of 120 farmers were selected using Yamane formula to determine the sample size while 10 media professionals were interviewed. Survey research design, research questionnaire and interview guide were the research instruments employed. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics involving frequency tables and percentages while content analysis was used to analyze the interviews. The findings showed that some films portray agriculture as a traditional farming profession while some other films and new media promote innovation, climate resilience and food sovereignty ($X = 3.63$, $SD = 1.59$) and films can inspire young people to consider agriculture as a viable career path rather than migrating to urban centers ($X = 3.88$, $SD = 1.32$). The findings also showed film as a useful tool for the visual demonstration of farming methods, technologies and best practices ($X = 3.66$, $SD = 1.58$). The research highlights the potential for Nigerian filmmakers and media practitioners to collaborate with agricultural stakeholders in fostering more accurate, engaging and transformative portrayals of food systems. Governmental agencies, NGOs and agrobusinesses should partner with Nollywood producers and screenwriters to create engaging and fact-based narratives that promote agricultural innovation and food security.

INTRODUCTION

Food security remains a critical issue in Nigeria, with challenges ranging from climate change and inefficient agricultural practices, to policy gaps and public apathy toward farming. The role of mass media, particularly cinema, in shaping the public's perception and behavior has been widely recognized (Bandura, 2001).

Film, as a powerful story-telling medium, has the potential to influence attitudes toward agricultural innovation, encouraging positive behavioral change among farmers, policymakers and consumers. Cinema has historically been used to promote social change and drive innovation in various sectors, including health, education and governance

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(Dovey, 2009). Films can serve as a tool for advocacy, providing visual and emotional engagement that enhances understanding and retention of key messages (Gerbner, 1998). In Nigeria, Nollywood; the country's prolific film industry, has been instrumental in shaping social narratives, addressing issues such as gender equality, corruption and cultural identity (Okome, 2007). However, its potential in influencing agricultural perceptions and food security awareness remains underexplored. The adoption of modern agricultural techniques in Nigeria has been slow, partly due to traditional farming practices, low literacy levels and resistance to change (FAO, 2020). Public's perception of agriculture is often shaped by cultural narratives, many of which depict farming as a profession of last resort (Olawoye, 2016). Films can play a transformative role by reshaping these narratives, presenting agriculture as a viable, profitable and innovative industry.

Documentaries and fictional films have been used worldwide to promote agricultural awareness. For instance, India's use of community-based cinema to educate farmers on sustainable practices has demonstrated measurable impacts on agricultural productivity (Panda and Kanchi, 2013). Similarly, in Kenya, films such as 'Shamba shape up' have been successful in demonstrating modern farming techniques (Zossou *et al.*, 2009). In Nigeria, integrating agricultural themes into Nollywood films could significantly alter the public's perception by fostering the enthusiasm for food security initiatives.

The Nigerian film industry, Nollywood, has a profound impact on shaping the public's opinions and cultural narratives. However,

most Nollywood films focus on themes such as crime, romance, and politics, with little emphasis on agriculture and food security (Okoro, 2020). Where agriculture is depicted, it is often associated with poverty, hardship and rural backwardness rather than innovation and economic opportunity (Adesina and Olajide, 2019). This negative portrayal can discourage the youths' participation in farming and reduce public trust in agricultural advancements.

Given the growing importance of films as a tool for social change, there is a need to explore how cinematic narratives can be leveraged to reshape perceptions of agricultural innovations and food security. Existing studies have highlighted the roles of films in influencing behavioral change in areas such as health, education and governance (Ekwueme and Asogwa, 2017) but researches on their impacts on agricultural development and food security in Nigeria remain scarce. This study seeks to bridge this gap by examining the roles of Nollywood and other cinematic productions in shaping the public's attitudes toward agricultural innovations. It aims to analyze the extent to which films can be used as an advocacy tool to promote modern farming practices, improve food security awareness and encourage the youths' engagement in agriculture. Addressing this research gap is crucial in fostering a positive agricultural narrative that supports national food security goals and sustainable development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Cinematic Narratives

Cinematic narratives refer to the story-telling techniques used in films to convey a story, emotions, and themes through visual, auditory and structural elements. It involves the interplay of mise-en-scène, cinematography,

editing, sound and narrative structure to immerse the audience in the story (Bradbury and Guadagno, 2020). Unlike traditional storytelling forms such as literature or theater, film is inherently visual and auditory. The screen becomes a canvas where images and sounds blend seamlessly to create a sensory-rich environment that envelops the viewer. The power of film lies not only in its ability to depict reality but also to construct entirely new worlds, from fantastical realms to historical epochs, drawing audiences into these narrative landscapes with unparalleled immediacy (Bilandzic and Sukalla, 2019).

Food Security

Food security, as defined by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2020), is a complex and multidimensional concept that encompasses the availability, accessibility, utilization and stability of food supplies. It necessitates guaranteeing that all individuals have access to adequate, safe and nutritious food to fulfil their dietary requirements and preferences (FAO, 2020).

The Agenda-Setting Theory

The agenda-setting theory, developed by McCombs and Shaw (1972), posits that the media play a significant role in shaping public opinion by setting the agenda for public discourse. According to McCombs and Shaw (1972), the media influence the public's opinions by highlighting specific issues and framing them in particular ways. In the context of promoting agricultural development and food security in Nigeria, the agenda-building theory can be applied by leveraging the media to shape public discourse on agricultural development and food security. Moreover, the agenda-building theory can be applied to influence policy-making by setting the agenda

for policy discussions. This approach can involve working with the media and policy-makers to highlight the importance of agricultural development and food security, showcasing successful agricultural initiatives and framing agricultural development and food security as critical issues that require urgent attention.

Empirical Reviews

Abubakar, Ango and Buhari (2009) carried out a study on Public Relations Strategies and Promotion of Agricultural Development and Food Security in Kebbi State. The agenda-building theory and the excellence theory were the theoretical frameworks used. A survey research design was used and 388 respondents completed questionnaires. According to the findings, the most popular public relations methods were media relations and partnerships with agricultural groups. While many respondents thought public relations in agricultural development was helpful, the survey indicated that techniques needed to be evaluated and improved on an ongoing basis. In light of the findings, the study stated that public relations technique is critical to boosting agricultural development and food security in Kebbi State. The study suggests that policymakers and organizations use both traditional and collaborative tactics, such as media relations and partnerships, to successfully distribute information and create sector-wide collaboration. Additionally, targeted outreach should be prioritized to better inform stakeholders and ongoing evaluation and improvement of strategies should be implemented to ensure their effectiveness.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The study made use of a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study are

media professionals from Ogun State chapter of Nigerian Union of Journalists and farmers in Abeokuta South. The study made used of a purposive sampling technique and a sample of 120 individuals were selected from the Ministry of Agriculture in Ogun State using Yamane formula to determine the sample size while 10 media professionals were interviewed using

research questionnaire and interview guide as research instruments. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics involving frequency tables and percentages while content analysis was used to analyze the interviews. SPSS version 23.0 software was used for the data analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1: Films’ influence on the public’s understanding, awareness and behavioral intentions toward agricultural practices and food security

S/N	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std Dev
1	Films serve as a powerful medium to raise awareness about agricultural innovations, food production challenges and the importance of food security	96 (80.0%)	11 (9.2%)	8 (6.7%)	5 (4.2%)	-	3.39	1.93
2	Films can inform audiences about modern farming techniques, climate-smart agriculture and governmental initiatives	52 (43.3%)	57 (47.5%)	11 (9.2%)	-	-	3.66	1.64
3	Films can inspire young people to consider agriculture as a viable career path rather than migrating to urban centers	14 (11.7%)	106 (88.3%)	-	-	-	3.88	1.32
4	Films and new media promote innovation, climate resilience and food sovereignty	51 (42.5%)	62 (51.7%)	7 (5.8%)	-	-	3.63	1.59

Table 1 shows that 96 (80.0%) of the respondents strongly agree that films serve as a powerful medium to raise awareness about agricultural innovations, food production challenges and the importance of food security, 11 (9.2%) of the respondents agree to the

statement, 8 (6.7%) were undecided while 5 (4.2%) disagreed on the statement. Also, 57 (47.5%) of the respondents agree that films can inform audiences about modern farming techniques, climate-smart agriculture and governmental initiatives, 52 (43.3%) of the

respondents strongly agree to the statement while 11 (9.2%) were undecided on the statement. In addition, 106 (88.3%) of the respondents agree that films can inspire young people to consider agriculture as a viable career path rather than migrating to urban centers while 14 (11.7%) of the respondents strongly

agree on the statement. Furthermore, 62 (51.7%) of the respondents agree that films and new media promote innovation, climate resilience and food sovereignty, 51 (42.5%) of the respondents strongly agree to the statement while 7 (5.8%) were undecided on the statement.

Table 2: The effectiveness of films as a medium for communicating agricultural innovations and food-related challenges to diverse Nigerian audiences

S/N	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std Dev
1	Films are useful for the visual demonstration of farming methods, technologies and best practices	44 (36.7%)	74 (61.7%)	2 (1.7%)	-	-	3.66	1.58
2	Through storytelling and relatable characters, films can evoke empathy and deeper understanding of food-related challenges such as climate change and food insecurity	78 (65.0%)	40 (33.3%)	2 (1.7%)	-	-	3.37	1.51
3	Films, especially those produced in local languages or with subtitles can help in making content relatable and accessible	95 (79.2%)	11 (9.2%)	14 (11.7%)	-	-	3.88	1.71
4	Involving local farmers in film production helps to ensure authenticity and give them a platform to share their experiences and innovations	33 (27.5%)	74 (61.7%)	8 (6.7%)	5 (4.2%)	-	3.04	1.85

Table 2 shows that 74 (61.7%) of the respondents agree that films are useful for the visual demonstration of farming methods, technologies and best practices, 44 (36.7%) of the respondents strongly agree to the statement while 2 (1.7%) of the respondents were

undecided. Also, 78 (65.0%) of the respondents strongly agree that through storytelling and relatable characters, films can evoke empathy and deeper understanding of food-related challenges such as climate change, food insecurity, 40 (33.3%) of the respondents agree

to the statement while 2 (1.7%) were undecided. Similarly, 95 (79.2%) of the respondents strongly agree that films, especially those produced in local languages or with subtitles can help in making content relatable and accessible, 11 (9.2%) of the respondents agree to the statement while 14 (11.7%) were undecided on the statement. Furthermore, 74 (61.7%) of the respondents agree that involving local farmers in film production helps ensure authenticity and give them a platform to share their experiences and innovations, 33 (27.5%) of the respondents strongly agree to the statement, 8 (6.7%) were undecided while 5 (4.2%) of the respondents disagree to the statement.

DISCUSSION

Abubakar, Ango and Buhari (2009) carried out a related survey but rather with emphasis on determining the potential correlation between public-relations techniques and the development of agriculture and food security. Their survey focused on local farmers in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

The findings of this study showed that films can influence the public's understanding, awareness, and behavioral intentions toward agricultural practices and food security as they serve as a powerful medium to raising awareness about agricultural innovations, food production challenges, and the importance of food security ($X = 3.39$, $SD = 1.93$), film and new media promotes innovation, climate resilience and food sovereignty ($X = 3.63$, $SD = 1.59$) and films can inspire young people to consider agriculture as a viable career path rather than migrating to urban centers ($X =$

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3.88, $SD = 1.32$). The findings also showed film as a useful tool for the visual demonstration of farming methods, technologies and best practices ($X = 3.66$, $SD = 1.58$), films can evoke empathy and deeper understanding of food-related challenges such as climate change, food insecurity through story telling ($X = 3.37$, $SD = 1.51$) and films, especially those produced in local languages or with subtitles can help in making content relatable and accessible ($X = 3.88$, $SD = 1.71$). These findings support the study of Suleiman *et al.* (2021) who reported that extension communication channels are effective in the dissemination of agroforestry technologies.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that films and new media promote innovations, climate resilience and food sovereignty. Films can also serve as a useful tool for the visual demonstration of farming methods, technologies and best practices. The study highlights the potential for Nigerian filmmakers and media practitioners to collaborate with agricultural stakeholders in, fostering more accurate, engaging and transformative portrayals of food systems.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. More awareness and training on agricultural innovation and food security should be created so as to enhance and equip farmers on the use of modern agricultural for effective agricultural productivity.
- ii. Governmental agencies, NGOs and agrobusinesses should partner with Nollywood producers and screenwriters to create engaging, fact-based narratives that promote agricultural innovations and food security.

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